

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC AND ELECTRICAL CONDUCTANCE
STUDIES IN THE FORMATION OF IRON^{III}-AMMONIUM
AURINTRICARBOXYLATE CHELATE

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The formation of a coloured chelate, having λ_{max} at 560 m μ , between ferric ion and ammonium aurintricarboxylate has been reported. It has been found that only one complex having the ratio 1:1 is formed in solution. Job's method of continued variation, using spectrophotometric and electrical conductance measurements, has been employed. The p_H of the system is not affected by chelation, showing that the phenolic hydrogens do not take part in the chelation process. The structure therefore has been suggested to involve a chelation between the quinoid oxygen and the adjacent carboxylic oxygen.

The spectrophotometric data have been used to calculate the formation constant, which works out to be 4.8×10^4 at 25°, while the free energy of formation is -6.4 Kcals.

Ammonium aurintricarboxylate, commonly known as Aluminon, has been employed for the colorimetric determination of aluminium (Johnson, "Organic Reagents for Metals", Chemical Publishing Co. Inc., New York, 1955), including the estimation of the metal in commercial materials and alloys (Banerjee, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, 29, 55; Bobtelsky and Ben Basset, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1956, 14, 439). Recently, Mukherji and Dey (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1956, 152, 424) have reported the formation of coloured lakes of various inorganic cations with ammonium aurintricarboxylate and suggested further use of this compound in colorimetric analysis of cations. They have studied the formation and stability of metal chelates, viz., those of copper, uranium, beryllium and of thorium (under publication elsewhere). Dey and Mukherji have also been able to utilise the colour formation in the micro-determination of copper, beryllium and iron (*Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., India*, 1957, 26A, 138) and thorium (unpublished).

Smith *et al.* (*J. Res. Natl. Bur. Standards*, 1938, 21, 105; *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 1334) observed that in order to obtain a stable colour the addition of alkali must be avoided. Mukherji and Dey (unpublished work) from electrical conductance studies found the reagent to behave as a colloidal electrolyte and recommended that physico-chemical measurements of complexes involving Aluminon should preferably be carried out in dilute solutions.

In this paper we have presented our results on the spectrophotometric and electrical conductance studies on ferric chloride-ammonium aurintricarboxylate system, in order to elucidate the composition and stability² of the chelate formed in solution.

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E X P E R I M E N T A L

Solutions of ferric chloride (BDH-Analar) and of ammonium aurintricarboxylate (BDH-Reagent) were prepared in double distilled water and standardised as usual. The Aluminium used was prepared by the method of Smith *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) as was ascertained from the manufacturers (British Drug Houses Ltd., Poole, *private communication*, December 1956). All solutions employed were always freshly prepared ones.

Optical measurements were made with a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer, using glass absorption cells of 10 mm light path, supplied by the manufacturer. The experiments were carried out in an air-conditioned room maintaining 25°. The individual solutions were kept in a thermostat maintained at 25° ± 0.01° and the mixtures were allowed to stand for 15 minutes in the thermostat to attain equilibrium.

For the measurement of electrical conductance, L & N Kohlrausch slidewire with an audiofrequency oscillator was employed. The conductivity cell was of the dip type, having a cell constant 0.132. The solutions and the mixture were kept in an electrically operated T & M Precision thermostat, maintaining a temperature of 32° ± 0.01°, before and during measurements. The total volume was kept 50 c.c. in every case. The p_{H} s were measured with L & N p_{H} -meter operated on 220 volts/50 cycles mains, using a glass electrode supplied with the instrument.

Nature of Complexes Formed.—Mixtures containing varying proportions of ferric chloride and ammonium aurintricarboxylate were prepared and the optical densities at different wave-lengths measured. In each mixture λ_{max} was observed at 560 m μ , showing that the nature of the complex species in all the mixtures was identical. Thus, it may be concluded that only one complex is formed in all the cases investigated.

Stoichiometry of the Components.—The composition of the complex was determined by Job's method of continued variation (*Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928; *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113; cf. Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437; 1942, 64, 1630). The total volume in each case was 50 c.c. Optical densities were measured at 560, 540, 460 and 440 m μ . It may be mentioned that at the dilutions and spectral regions employed, ferric chloride solutions have no absorption. The results are represented graphically in Figs. 1-4. In the figures, the difference of optical density of the mixture and that which would be shown by the reagent above, if no chelation occurs, is plotted against the composition of the mixture. The results of electrical conductance studies are plotted in Fig. 5. Here too, the difference in observed conductance of the mixture and that expected in case of no reaction between the metal ion and the reagent, is plotted against the composition of the mixture. In the legends, c_1 represents the concentration of ferric chloride, while c_2 that of ammonium aurintricarboxylate, i.e., $p = c_1/c_2$.

FIG. 3

$\lambda=440$ m μ , $p=1$,
 A: $c=1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$,
 B: $c=2.0 X$ "
 $\lambda=540$ m μ , $p=1$,
 C: $c=1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$,
 D: $c=2.0 X$ "

FIG. 2

$\lambda=560$ m μ : A: $c=2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$; $\hat{p}=0.66$
 B: $c=1.66$ " $\hat{p}=1.5$
 C: $c=2.0 X$ " $\hat{p}=0.55$
 $\lambda=460$ " D: $c=2.5 X$ " $\hat{p}=1$
 " E: $c=1.66 X$ " $\hat{p}=1$

FIG. 1

$\lambda=560$ m μ , $p=1$,
 Curve A: $c=2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$
 B: " $c=2.0 X$ "
 C: " $c=1.66 X$ "
 D: " $c=1.0 X$ "

FIG. 4

$\lambda = 460 \text{ m}\mu$,
 A: $c = 2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$; $p = 0.66$
 B: $c = 1.66 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$; $p = 1.5$
 C: $c = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$; $p = 0.5$

FIG. 5

Curve A: $c = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; $p = 1$.
 B: $c = 0.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; $p = 1$.

FIG. 6

$\lambda = 560 \text{ m}\mu$, $p = 1$.
 A: $c = 2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$
 B: $c = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$
 C: $c = 1.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$

DISCUSSION

It may be seen from the figures that in every case the peaks of the curves occur at a ratio of 1:1 of the reactants. It has also been found by p_H measurements that the acidity of the system does not increase on mixing solutions of ferric chloride and ammonium aurintricarboxylate. This shows that hydrogen ions are not liberated as a result of chelation and, hence, the phenolic hydrogen does not take part in the reaction. It may therefore be concluded that the chelation occurs between the quinoid oxygen and the adjacent carboxylic oxygen, as shown below :

(I) Chelating agent.

(II) Iron^{III} chelate.

For the calculation of the formation constant, we have employed the optical density data and have followed the method described by Mukherji and Dey (this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 461). The method of continued variation was employed and optical densities of mixtures of various compositions were measured at a fixed wave-length. The observed optical density has been plotted against $[M]/[M] + [R]$ ($[M]$ = concentration of metal ion and $[R]$ that of chelating agent). In Fig. 6, such a graph is shown for the system investigated. In our case, the metal ion is colorless (at the concentrations and wave-lengths used), while the chelating agent is coloured. Hence, with the progressive addition of metal ions, $[R]$ decreases, and it may be assumed that in the descending portions of the curves, where the metal ions are in large excess, most of the chelating agent is bound up in the complex. Therefore, in this portion of the curve, optical density of the free chelating agent does not contribute substantially to the optical density of the system. The observed optical density may, hence, be regarded as the colour of the complex alone. Thus, in Fig. 6, in curves A, B and C, where the optical densities are the same, (say 0.2), the respective amounts of the complex may be taken to be identical.

In the system, where an 1:1 complex is formed,

i.e., $m = n = 1$, the formation constant,

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-x)} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where x = concentration of the complex at equilibrium, and a and b are initial concentrations of the metal ion and the chelating agent respectively. Taking two concentrations a_1, a_2 and b_1, b_2 of the reactants, having the same optical density, i.e., the same value of x , we have

$$K = \frac{x}{(a_1-x)(b_1-x)} = \frac{x}{(a_2-x)(b_2-x)} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or } x = \frac{a_1 b_1 - a_2 b_2}{(a_1 + b_1) - (a_2 + b_2)} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Knowing the value of x from equation (3), the value of K can be found out by substitution in equation (1).

We have calculated the value of the formation constant of ferric ammonium aurintricarboxylate chelate to be 4.8×10^4 .

The free energy of formation of the chelate has been calculated with the help of the expression :

$$\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where ΔF° is the standard free-energy change, R , the gas constant and T , the absolute temperature.

The free energy of formation of ferric ammonium aurintricarboxylate works out to be -6.4 Kcals. at 25° .